

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN DEVELOPING WRITTEN SPEECH IN THE PRIMARY CLASS

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Abstract. This article discusses innovative pedagogical approaches in the process of developing written speech. The effectiveness of the formation of written speech based on interactive methods and digital technologies, and the results of the experiment show that innovative methods are an important factor in the development of students' written speech skills.

Keywords: written speech, innovative approach, pedagogical approach, interactive methods, digital technologies, educational effectiveness.

Introduction. In the modern education system, the development of students' written speech is one of the important pedagogical tasks. Written speech reflects a person's level of thinking, worldview, and culture of communication. In today's conditions of globalization and digitalization, it is not enough to be limited to traditional teaching methods. Therefore, the introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches to the educational process is becoming an urgent issue.

Innovative approaches to the development of written speech are one of the main directions of modern education, which includes information technologies, interactive methods and project-based learning. Methods such as developmental education, creative writing, cluster method and portfolio serve to increase students' independent thinking, literacy and creative abilities, as a result of which speech competence is formed. The main innovative pedagogical approaches to the development of written speech are:

- use of information and communication technologies and presentations. This increases students' interest in writing and ensures interactivity.
- creative writing is teaching students to think creatively and express their feelings in writing. This uses methods such as free topics and writing stories.
- cluster method - a method that helps to visually organize ideas on a topic and systematize written speech.

- project-based learning - students conduct research in groups or independently and present the final result in writing (report, project).

These approaches, along with developing students' written speech, teach them to think independently and critically, and increase their level of literacy. In the traditional educational process, the development of written speech is mainly limited to writing dictations, statements, and essays. This does not sufficiently develop independent thinking and creativity in students. Therefore, the use of innovative pedagogical approaches in the development of written speech becomes a pressing issue. The aim is to substantiate the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical approaches in the development of written speech and provide practical examples of their application in the educational process.

Written speech develops the student's:

- logical thinking;
- grammatical literacy;

- ability to express independent and creative thoughts. A student with developed written speech can express his/her thoughts clearly, fluently and reasonably. The content of innovative pedagogical approaches. Competency-based approach - this approach is aimed at forming students' skills in applying knowledge in practice. In the development of written speech, students' speech competence is strengthened by writing essays, articles, letters, applications, project reports. Use of interactive methods - interactive methods increase student activity. Using methods such as "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Fishbone", "Insert", students learn to work on the text, analyze and draw written conclusions. Use of information and communication technologies - ICT tools create great opportunities for the development of written speech.

Editing text on online platforms, blogging, and creating electronic portfolios increase students' written literacy and increase their interest in the lesson. Project-based learning - during project activities, students independently search for, analyze, and present information in written form. This develops written speech, as well as critical thinking skills. Results and discussion - Lessons organized on the basis of innovative pedagogical approaches significantly improve students' written speech. Students gain freedom in composing texts, learn to write based on their own opinions, and demonstrate a creative approach.

In conclusion, the use of innovative pedagogical approaches in the development of written speech increases the effectiveness of education. These approaches turn the student into an active subject of the educational process and serve to form an independent, creative and critical thinking person. Therefore, it

is advisable to widely introduce innovative approaches to the process of forming written speech in the modern education system.

References:

1. Ishmuhamedov R.J. Innovative technologies in education. – Tashkent: Iste’dod, 2012.
2. Yo’ldoshev J.G., Usmonov S.A. Fundamentals of pedagogical technology. – Tashkent: O’qituvati, 2004.
3. Saidahmedov N. New pedagogical technologies. – Tashkent: Moliya, 2003.
4. Husanboyeva K. Methodology of teaching the native language. – Tashkent: Fan va tehnologiya, 2015.
5. Abdullayeva M. Issues of speech culture and development of written speech. – Tashkent: Fan, 2018.
6. Alimardanova , S. , & Shoyimova , G. . (2025). The importance of the teacher’s creative abilities in developing the speech of primary school students. Pedagogy and psychology in the modern world: theoretical and practical research, 4(7), 151–153. izvlecheno ot <https://www.inlibrary.uz/index.php/zdpp/article/view/80824>
7. Alimardanova , S. . (2025). Axborot texnologiyalarining og‘zaki nutq rivojiga ta’siri. теоретические аспекты становления педагогических наук, 4(8), 11–14. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/tafps/article/view/80920>

